

MATHEMATICS

IN THE 9TH GRADE OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS "QUADRATIC FUNCTION" TECHNOLOGY OF MASTERING MATERIALS FOR THE EDUCATIONAL UNIT

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Abstract

In the article, the content of the skills intended to become the subject of students in the process of teaching materials for the "Quadratic function" educational unit, which is included in the content of the Mathematics subject in the IX class of general education schools, is presented. In the "Quadratic function" educational unit, attention is directed to the place of the content elements that perform the "enabling function" in the formation of the mentioned skills and to the technology of turning them into actions in the students' cognition. Transformable elements in the "Quadratic function" educational unit "Graph of Quadratic Function", "Zeros of the quadratic function", "The general picture of the quadratic function. Problem solving using quadratic function", function and its graph. It is considered appropriate to turn it into a system on the topics of "generalizing tasks". It should be noted that the task system, which serves as a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements presented by the students, should contain verbs that are required to be performed in the topics. Examples of tasks of that kind are included in the content of the work. $y = |x|$

Keywords: teaching process; teaching unit; content lines; standard; system; subsystem; paradigm; assignment; methodological system; quadratic function; graph of quadratic function; parabola; vertex of a parabola; axis of symmetry of the parabola; expression forms of quadratic function; zeros of quadratic function; modular function.

The actuality of the subject.

There are recommendations that are useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the currently used textbook complex and various educational literature about mathematics teaching units, basic standards, substandards, and defined topics. This is very useful in terms of teaching the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is logical, most didactic problems are eternal. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system of the teaching process adequate to it should be improved. Based on this logic, we claim the relevance of the research of the topic "Methodical system of teaching the specified topics for the realization of the sub-standards of the unit of study "Quadratic function" in class IX.

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research.

Scientific sources indicate that "training" and "teaching activity" are one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic of teaching activity, it does not cover all its aspects. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity.[2;150]

According to our opinion, training is a way of implementing education, and the fact that spiritual learning, memorizing what has been learned, and acquiring

the experience of creative activity based on it depends on the way of learning (the dialectic of the content and form of cognitive action). Forming a model of educational implementation in didactics is a perennial problem.

The technology of education implementation (methodology in the traditional approach) has its own system [1]. The expected result in the mentioned technological system is determined by the state of movement of the selected content. A technological system is available for each educational unit. It is not accidental that the selection of the educational unit is brought to the center of attention in the design of the system in question.[3; 282-283]

"Quadratic function" teaching unit has a unique place in the mathematics subject in secondary schools. In the process of teaching the topics covered in the "Quadratic function" educational unit, the content standards-"2.2.2. Solve the system of two-variable equations, one of which is linear and the other of two degrees; 2.2.3. The square solves the inequality.

- constructs the graph of a quadratic function by making a table of values;

- constructs the graph of the quadratic function using the graph of the function; $y = x^2$

- constructs the graph of the quadratic function according to the expression forms; $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ and $y = a(x - p)(x - q)$

- graphs and examines a quadratic function according to its general form;

$$y = ax^2 + bx + c$$

■ solves problems by applying the quadratic function;

■ graphs the quadratic function according to the expression forms.

$$y = a(x - m)^2 + n \vee y = a(x - p)(x - q)$$

■ defines the zeros of the function;

■ constructs the graph of a quadratic function by making a table of values;

■ constructs the graph of the quadratic function using the graph of the function;

$$y = x^2$$

■ constructs the graph of the quadratic function according to the expression forms; $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ and $y = a(x - p)(x - q)$

■ defines the zeros of the function;

■ general quadratic function $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ builds and explores graphics that match his image

■ solves problems by applying the quadratic function;

■ $y = |x|$ constructs the graphs of the functions and using the graph of the function; $y = 2|x|$ $y = |x + 2|$ $y = -|x + 2|$

■ using the graph of the function $y = |x|$ builds graphs of the functions

$$y = |x| + 2 \text{ and}$$

$$y = -|x| + 2.$$

"Quadratic function" in the mathematics subject of IX grade of general education schools. Graph of a quadratic function. Expression forms of quadratic function It is enough to spend 5 hours teaching the subject. First, let's emphasize that the said Study unit It is recommended to take advantage of Internet addresses [13] in the teaching of materials on the following concepts - quadratic function; graph of quadratic function; parabola; vertex of a parabola; axis of symmetry of the parabola; expression forms of quadratic function; zeros of quadratic function; the modular function enables them to be enriched with considerations that express the relationships between them.

In the teaching of the subject, students' attention is focused on the concept of "quadratic function", $y = ax^2$, $y = x^2 + n$, $y = (x - m)^2$, $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ is directed to the graphs of quadratic functions in the form, and the presentation of the quadratic function in different forms.

By involving students in the research task, a cognitive requirement is created in them to study the concept of a quadratic function, and it is stated that when $a \neq 0$, the function in the form $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ is called a quadratic function. The graph of a quadratic function is a parabola. When $a=1$, $b=0$, $c=0$, the quadratic function takes the form $y = x^2$, and its graph vertex (0;0) is a parabola with a point.

It is advisable to start the work of familiarizing students with the graph of the function $y = ax^2$ by discussing the functions

$y = x^2$, $y = 2x^2$, $y = \frac{1}{2}x^2$, $y = -2x^2$. Students should conclude that 1) the graph of function $y = 2x^2$ is obtained by "tightening" parabola $y = x^2$ 2 times over the abscissa Axis; 2) the graph of function $y = \frac{1}{2}x^2$ is obtained by "squeezing" parabola $y = x^2$ 2

times over the abscissa axis; 3) parabola $y = -x^2$ is obtained by symmetry transformation of Parabola $y = x^2$. A similar rule is justified by the fact that the parabolas $y = -2x^2$ and $y = 2x^2$ are symmetric in relation to the abscissa axis. [10; 23-24]

The learner should become the subject of information about the graph of the function as follows: $y = ax^2$

$y = ax^2$ The graph of the function is a parabola with the vertex located at the coordinate origin, the axis of symmetry being the ordinate axis.

• $a > 0$ when , the arms of the parabola point up, and when $a < 0$

• $|a| > 1$ when the parabola is stretched in the vertical direction from the abscissa axis and its branches are "stretched" with respect to the parabola. $y = x^2$

• $|a| < 1$ when the parabola is compressed in the vertical direction to the abscissa axis, $y = x^2$ it "expands" with respect to the parabola. [4; 463]

The work of familiarizing students with the graph of the function

$$y = x^2 + n, y = x^2,$$

$y = x^2 + 1$, it is known that it is advisable to start by discussing the functions

$$y = x^2 - 2.$$

From this, students must conclude that the parabola corresponding to the function

$y = x^2 + 1$ is the sliding of the parabola $y = x^2$ along the Oy axis by 1 unit up, and the vertex point is the point (0;1). The parabola corresponding to the function $y = x^2 - 2$ is obtained by sliding the parabola $y = x^2$ along the Oy axis by 2 units, which is its Vertex Point (0;-2). [8; 50]

Students can come to the conclusion without difficulty that due to the limit (number) n , the position of the parabola changes vertically along the Oy axis, and it is important that the vertex of the parabola is correctly marked.

The student must have mastered the information on the graph of the function

$$y = ax^2 + n \text{ as follows:}$$

The graph of the function $y = ax^2 + n$ is that the parabola $y = ax^2$ is shifted along the Oy axis.

• The Parabola is shifted along the Oy axis by $|n|$ unit; down when $n < 0$ and up when $n > 0$

• The vertex of the parabola is located at the point. (0; n)

In order for students to assimilate generalized information about the graph of the function $y = (x - m)^2$, their attention is focused on the graphs of the functions

$y = (x - 2)^2$ and $y = (x + 3)^2$. They conclude that by sliding parabola $y = x^2$ by 3 units to the left, $y = (x + 3)^2$, $y = (x - 2)^2$ parabola is obtained by sliding parabola

$y = x^2$ by 2 units to the right. the limit m changes the position of the parabola along the axial axis (horizontal). [5; 354]

The student should have mastered the following general information about the graph of a function: $y = a(x - m)^2$

- if $m > 0$, the parabola is shifted to the right along the axis of the Axis, and if $m < 0$, to the left.
- the straight line $x=m$ is the axis of symmetry of the parabola.
- m corresponds to the abscissa of the vertex of the parabola. The vertex of the parabola becomes $(m; 0)$.

Students are told that the graph of the function $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ is built according to the graph of the

Quadratic function	The graph
1. Spelling by Vertex or with the separation of the full square $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$	The vertex of the parabola: $(m; n)$ Axis of symmetry: $x=m$
2. With respect to the points of intersection with the abscissa axis, write $y = a(x - p)(x - q)$	The graph intersects the Ox axis at points p and q. Axis of symmetry: it is the middle perpendicular of the piece with the ends $(p;q)$ and $(q;q)$. Abscissa of the vertex $m=(p+q):2$

In all cases, if $a > 0$, the arms of the parabola are directed upwards, while if $a < 0$, the arms of the parabola are directed downwards. The vertex point of the parabola and the points of intersection with the coordinate axes are important points of the parabola. In the process of teaching the subject, students should acquire the skills to take the necessary steps related to the construction of the quadratic function. Here are the steps to build a parabola:

- * The vertex is found and marked on the coordinate plane;
- * The points of intersection with the Ox axis (if any) and with the Oy axis are found
- * The axis of symmetry is defined;
- * Several points on the parabola are marked according to the axis of symmetry;
- * A parabola passing through the marked points is constructed. [8; 53]

It is useful for students to work on tasks related to identifying important points. Examples of such tasks include:

■ Quadratic function by data $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ write in the form:

- a) whose vertex is at the point $(0;0)$ and passes through the point $(6;9)$; b) whose vertex is at the point $(0;3)$ and passes through the point $(3;24)$; c) whose vertex is at the point $(2;5)$ and passes through the point $(4;-11)$; d) whose vertex is at the point $(-3;-10)$ and passes through the point $(2;-5)$.

■ Construct the graphs of the given functions. Mark the coordinates of the vertex and the axis of symmetry on the graph:

1) $y = (x - 3)^2$; 2) $y = 3(x - 2)^2 - 1$; 3) $y = -2(x - 2)^2 + 4$;

4) $y = \frac{11}{2}(x - 3)^2 + 2$

■ Why is the parabola $y = x^2 + 3$ shifted up $y = x^2$ by its axis in the positive direction to construct the parabola, $y = (x - 3)^2$, and to the right Ox along the axis when constructing the graph of the function?

■ The number of points of intersection of the graph of a quadratic function with the axis Ox is not always the same. Is this opinion also true for Oy reading? Prove it.

function $y = x^2$, making a generalization in the context of what was considered above. On the basis of the selected sample, discretion is clarified. It is concluded that $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ is located at the vertex Point $(m;n)$ of the parabola. The axis of symmetry of this parabola is the straight line $x=m$.

In the process of teaching the subject, it should be clear to students that the graph of a quadratic function can be presented in different forms:

Work sheet

Name surname.....

History.....

• $y = x^2$ according to the graph of the function and constructs the graph of the functions. $y = x^2 + n$ and $y = (x - m)^2$
 $y = x^2$ Graph the given functions using the graph of function .

a) $g(x) = x^2 + 1$; b) $p(x) = x^2 - 3$; c) $r(x) = (x + 1)^2$; ç) $k(x) = (x - 3)^2$.

Explanation:.....

Work sheet

Name surname.....

History.....

• $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ constructs the graph of the given quadratic function.

Plot the graphs of the function according to the vertices and the line of symmetry.

1) $y = (x - 3)^2 + 2$; 2) $y = (x + 3)^2 - 1$; 3) $y = -(x + 3)^2 - 4$;

4) $y = -(x + 3)^2 + 3$. [9]

It is enough to devote 1 hour to teaching the topic "Zeros of quadratic function". In the teaching process of this topic, students' attention is directed to the points on the abscissa axis of the graph of the function. It is clarified that the value of the function is equal to zero at the mentioned points.

Students are informed that the values of the argument that make the function zero are called the zeros of this function. It is possible to determine the number of zeros by the values of a and n for the function $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$

• according to the value of a , it can be said that the arms of the parabola are directed up or down.

• by the value of n , it can be said that the vertex of the parabola is located above the abscissa axis, below or on the abscissa axis.

The teaching of the topic is continued based on the following examples of determining the number of points of intersection with the abscissa axis according to the vertex of the parabola and the upward or downward direction of its arms.

An example:

- a) $f(x) = 0,8x^2 - 3$;
 b) $f(x) = 2(x + 1)^2$
 c) $f(x) = -3(x + 2)^2 - 1$. [7; 310]

Learning tasks on the topic "Zeros of a quadratic function" are offered to students as a whole class and group work. Examples of such tasks include:

❖ Determine the number of points in common with the abscissa axis of the graphs of the following functions:

- a) $y = 5x^2 - 7$;
 b) $y = -2(x + 1)^2$;
 c). $y = \frac{1}{4}(x - 5)^2 - 9$

- ❖ a) $y = 5(x - 15)^2 - 100$;
 b) $y = -4x^2 + 14$;
 c) $y = (x + 18)^2 - 8$

❖ without constructing their graph for functions, determine: 1) the direction of the arms of the parabola; 2) the coordinates of the vertex; 3) the equation of the axis of symmetry; 4) the number of points of intersection with the axis Ox .

❖ (10;0) and (4;0) the points of intersection of the vertex with the abscissa axis of the parabola, the ordinate of which is -9, are: a) write the formula of the function; B) write down the coordinates of three pairs of points that are symmetric in relation to the axis of symmetry with the location on this parabola; c) build a graph.

❖ Graph the functions. Find the distance between the points of intersection with the abscissa axis. Write the equation of the axis of symmetry:

- a) $f(x) = x^2 - 4x + 3$; b) $f(x) = x^2 + 2x - 8$.

❖ The points of intersection with the coordinate axes of the parabola are given. Given these data, find the coordinates of the vertex of the parabola:

- a) (3;0), (-1;0), (0;6);
 b) (-2;0), (-3;0), (0;4);
 c) (-3;0), (1;0), (0;3).

In this teaching unit, the self-contained "general picture of the quadratic function. It is advisable to devote 6 hours to teaching the topic" problem solving with the application of a quadratic function". The first exercise aimed at teaching the subject can begin with the work of bringing the quadratic function given in the form $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ to the form $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ by separating the integer square. With discussions with students,

$$y = ax^2 + bx + c = a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} \quad \text{is}$$

determined and $m = -\frac{b}{2a}$, $n = \frac{4ac - b^2}{4a}$ is accepted. Thus, $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ is obtained. The axis of symmetry of the parabola $y = a(x - m)^2 + n$ students should know that $x = m$ is the straight line, the vertex Point $(m; n)$. Where $m = \frac{-b}{2a}$; $n = \frac{-D}{4a}$; $D = b^2 - 4ac$. [12; 271]

By involving students in the activity on several samples, their skills are formed to bring the quadratic function given in the form $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ to the form

$$y = a(x - m)^2 + n$$

of dividing a complete square is formed.

Through joint discussions with students, the properties of $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ the quadratic function are summarized as follows:

• if $a > 0$, the arms of the parabola with the graph of the quadratic function are directed upward, and if $a < 0$, the arms of the parabola are directed downward;

• The abscissa of the vertex of the parabola is $-\frac{b}{2a}$, and the equation of the axis of symmetry is $x = -\frac{b}{2a}$.

• The parabola intersects the ordinate axis at the point $(0; c)$;

• $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ the value of the ordinate of the vertex of the function (i.e.n) if $a > 0$ is the smallest value of the function, if $a < 0$ it is the largest value of the function. [6,400-401]

These values are called the minimum and maximum values of the quadratic function.

• The set of values taken by the argument is the domain of the function;

• The values received by the function form the set of values of the function.

$y = ax^2 + bx + c$ is the set of all real numbers less than or equal to its maximum value ($y \leq n$) if the set of values for the function $a < 0$; and if $a > 0$ is the set of all real numbers greater than or equal to its minimum value ($y \geq n$).

• The function increases if the graph "goes up" from left to right, the function decreases if the graph "goes down" from left to right. When $a > 0$ $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ the function decreases in the range $(-\infty; -\frac{b}{2a}]$, and increases in the range $[-\frac{b}{2a}; +\infty)$. When $a < 0$ $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ the function increases in the range $(-\infty; -\frac{b}{2a}]$, and decreases in the range $[-\frac{b}{2a}; +\infty)$.

Examination of its function $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ based on a specially prepared slide is included in the teaching process of the subject. In this direction, in order to develop students' skills, it is recommended to use learning and creative application tasks in the form of whole class and group work. The following tasks can be taken as an example of what is said:

❖ Eldar draws different rectangles. But the sum of the length and width of these rectangles is always 12 cm.

a) Make a table with different values of latitude and longitude.

b) Write the dependence of the area of the rectangle on its width as a function.

c) What is the largest area of the rectangle when its width is in centimeters?

❖ The transport company engaged in passenger transportation serves 200 passengers daily. The price of one ticket is 5 manats. The owner of the company thinks that every 50 penny increase in price leads to a decrease of 10 passengers.

a) How many times will the company get the maximum revenue from ticket sales if it raises prices like this?

b) How many manats can the daily income of the company be at most with these price increases?

❖ Measure the height h (in m) that the ball thrown up Rises After t seconds it can be found by the formula $h = -5t^2 + 20t + 1$

a) After how many seconds will the ball reach a height of 16 m?

b) What is the maximum height the ball will rise?

c) How many seconds will the ball be in the air?

❖ At what value of k is the smallest value of the function

$$y = x^2 + 6x + k \text{ equal to } 1?$$

Work sheet

Name surname.....

History.....

* Quadratic function $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ he builds and explores the graphics that match his image.

1) $y = -x^2 - 6x + 4$; 2) $y = x^2 - 6x + 4$;
3) $y = -x^2 - 4$; 4) $y = -x^2 - 6x - 9$ in accordance with its functions, determine the following:

* writing with vertices (separation of a complete square);

* vertex;

* the equation of the axis of symmetry;

* the price of the ABG and AKG;

* The destination area and price range;

* Ox intersection with the axis.

* Oy intersection with the axis.[9]

" $y = |x|$ function and its graph. It is enough to devote 2 hours to teaching the topic "Generalizing exercises". It is useful to start the teaching of the subject with the concept of the absolute value of a real number by giving the following information to the students. It is stated that the absolute value of a real number x is called the number x if X is positive, the number $(-x)$ if it is negative, and the number zero if it is zero. The absolute value of a number is also called its modulus. Module is derived from the Latin word modulus - measure. the absolute value of the number x is denoted in the form $|x|$. This sign was first used by the German scientist Karl Weiershrass(1815-1897). What is said about the absolute value of the number x can be written with the following equality:

$$|x| = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } x = 0 \text{ or in short } |x| = \\ -x, & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} x, & \text{when } x \geq 0, \\ -x, & \text{when } x < 0. \end{cases} \text{ [11; 8].}$$

As a continuation of such restorative activity, students are assigned to the training work on the construction of the graph of the function $y=|x|$. It turns out that the graph of the function $y=|x|$ is symmetric with respect to the Oy axis. Because the point $(-x;y)$ of the graph, which is symmetric with respect to the Oy axis with each point $(x;y)$, also belongs to the graph. The graph of the function $y=|x|$ consists of two rays with denticles of I and II quarters. The point $(0; 0)$ is the vertex point of the graph. It is advisable to continue the educational process by involving students in two investigative activities, such as:

a) examine graphs of functions $y=|x|$, $y=2|x|$, $y=-|x|$, $y=-2|x|$ built in the same coordinate system;

b) explore graphs of functions $y=|x+2|$ and $y=|x-1|$, as well as functions $y=|x|+2$ and $y=|x|-4$. As a result of these studies, the following generalization (basic properties of the function $y=a|x-m|+n$) is formulated:

• The graph of the function $y = a|x - m| + n$ is that the graph of the function $y = a|x|$ is shifted to $|m|$ unit horizontal (right when $m>0$, left when $m<0$), $|n|$ unit vertical (up when $n>0$, down when $n<0$) it is to be swiped.

• $(m; n)$ is the vertex of the graph, and the graph is symmetric with respect to the line $x=m$.

• When $a>0$ the rays that make up the graph point upward, and when $a<0$ they point downward. [8; 66]

Based on custom-made slide $y=-|x+2|+3$ it is advisable to focus the attention of students on the construction of the graph of the function, on the graph and examples of writing the corresponding function according to the given points, such a continuation of the work becomes useful. In order to develop students ' skills in this direction, it is also necessary to use learning and creative application tasks in the form of general class and group work. Examples of tasks can include:

Determine whether the graphs of the given functions are: a) "compressed" or "expanded " in relation to the graph of the function $y=|x|$, or are of the same width; b) determine whether the branches of the graph are directed down or up; c) determine the graph of the functions.

$y = |x|$ construct according to the graph of the function.

$$y = \frac{1}{2}|x|; 2) y = |x| + 4; 3) y = 2|x + 6| - 10.$$

Perform the tasks according to the given functions (examples are selected from the textbook or from various sources):

1) Determine the intersection points with the Axis and Oy axes;

2) plot the graphs on the same coordinate plane;

3) determine the destination area and the set of prices.

a) $y = 3|x|$ or $y = |3x|$; b) $y = |x - 6|$ or $y = |x| - 6$.

In order to generalize the knowledge and skills acquired in this educational unit, it is recommended to take advantage of the task examples below.

*The point $A(2,3)$ is above the parabola $y = x^2 + 2x + c$. Indicate the vertex of this parabola.

A) $(-1;6)$; B) $(2;4)$; C) $(-1;-6)$; D) $(-2;3)$.

7. find b if the abscissa of the vertex of the parabola $y = -x^2 + bx + 6$ is 2

A) -4 B) 4 C) 2 D) -2

* at what point does the parabola $y=(x-2)(x+3)$ intersect the Oy axis?

A) $(0;2)$ B) $(0;-3)$ C) $(0; -6)$ D) $(-6;0)$

*graph the function $y = |x - 1|$

* $v_0 = 24 \text{ m/san}$ from the ground surface of the ball thrown up at the starting speed dependence of distance h (in M) on flight time t (san) $h = 24t - 5t^2$ given by the formula.

a) find the highest height at which the ball rises;

b) how many seconds after the throw will the ball fall to the ground ?

* at what value of c is the smallest value of the function $y = x^2 - 2x + c$ -is the value equal to 5?

* Place an arbitrary parabola in the coordinate system and write the formula of the quadratic function according to that graph and find its smallest value.

* $y = x^2$ parabola horizontally 2 units to the right, vertical of which quadratic function when shifted 3 units down the scale is the schedule available?

* A rectangle with sides of 3 cm and 5 cm is given. At what value of a will the area of the obtained rectangle be the largest if we reduce the large side by a cm and increase the small side by a cm?

The result. 1) In the process of teaching the topics covered in the “Quadratic function” educational unit, the selection and application of task types should be focused on in order for students to become subjects of verbs based on expected results;

2) In the process of teaching materials for the “Quadratic function” educational unit, the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of the students’ active mathematical vocabulary should be considered as an important didactic requirement;

3) It is recommended to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching materials on the “Quadratic function” educational unit;

4) Since the materials of the “Quadratic function” educational unit belong to the “Algebra and functions” content line, in the real pedagogical process, they are used both as a whole (with the content covered by the mathematics subject as a whole) and in parts belonging to each content line (subsystems of the other four content lines)) dialectic unity (“system-structure” approach-whole-part relations) should be expected between its elements;

5) The expectation of the “opportunity-movement-quality” paradigm in the selection of tasks and making them into a system has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

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